

DAMAGE IN AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS IN TENSION OR SHEAR-OUT MODE FAILURE

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ABSTRACT

Numerical simulations were performed by using the computer code, "PDBOLT", to study the effect of ply orientation on damage growth in bolted composite joints subjected to a tensile loading, and to predict residual strength of the joints damaged previously by a pre-load. Based on the calculations, it was found that ply orientation and geometry have significant effects on both strength and internal damage growth of bolted joints in laminated composites. The load-damage area curve generated by the code could be very useful in selection ply orientation for the design of bolted composite joints. The calculations also indicated that initial damage had a limited effect on the ultimate load (residual strength) of the joints as long as the damage was confined to a local area. As a result, the information on damage progression is very important in designing bolted composite joints, in addition to the knowledge of joint strength.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanically fastened joints in laminated composites have been widely utilized in constructing aerospace structures. Prediction of strength and failure modes of these joints is an important task by which design of these structures could be significantly affected, since joint failure could lead to a catastrophic failure of the structures. As a consequence, significant efforts have been made in developing analyses for predicting the failure strengths and failure modes of bolted composite joints [1-9]. However, to date, most of the analyses considered that the joints behaved only linear-elastically and assumed no damage occurred in materials before they totally failed. Therefore, the majority of the analyses were empirical or semi-empirical.

As a result, little information is known about damage accumulating in composite joints during mechanical loading and about residual strength of the joints after a pre-load. It is believed that an optimal design of bolted joints in laminated composites cannot be achieved without having this information. Recently, a model was developed by the author et al [10] which can simulate damage progression and predict the extent of damage and the types of

damage in laminated composites containing stress concentrations. It was then successfully extended to predict the failure of bolted composite joints which failed in tension or shear-out mode [11]. A computer code, "PDBOLT", based on the model was developed [11] which was capable of assessing damage accumulated in composites as well as predicting failure strength of bolted composite joints in tension or shear-out mode failure.

Therefore, the objective of this study was to use the computer code to study the effect of ply orientation on damage growth in bolted composite joints subjected to a tensile loading, and to predict residual strength of the joints damaged previously by a pre-load.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Consider a laminate containing a pin-loaded hole as shown in Figure 1. The ply orientation of the laminate can be arbitrary but must be symmetrical with respect to its middle plane. The laminate is loaded by a uniform tensile load through a pin inserted into the hole (see Figure 1). It is desired to find

- 1) the damage accumulated in the laminate as a function of the applied load,
- 2) the effect of ply orientation on the damage progression in the joint, and
- 3) the residual strength of the laminate after a pre-load.

METHOD OF APPROACH

In this investigation the computer code previously developed was used to perform the calculations. The analytical model on which the code was based was described in detail in Refs. 10 and 11, hence, it will not be presented here. Basically, the analysis consists of two major parts: stress analysis and failure analysis. Stress and strain distributions inside the material were calculated by the use of a nonlinear finite element analysis based on the updated Lagrange Formulation with the consideration of material and geometrical nonlinearities [10-13].

Damage and subsequent failure in the laminate was predicted by a proposed failure analysis which contained a set of failure criteria and a property degradation model. Numerical algorithms were developed for redistributing stresses and strains within and near the damaged area in the laminate.

NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

Strength Prediction

Numerical results generated from the computer code were compared with strength data of bolted joints in laminated composites made of T300/1034-C Graphite-Epoxy prepregs [8]. The material properties used in the calculations are listed in Table 1. The data and the calculated results are presented in Figure 2, including seven different ply orientations and various dimensions. The solid lines in the figure represent the calculated results, and the open circle and triangle symbols indicate the data.

TABLE 1
Properties of T300/1034-C Graphite-Epoxy Composites

Ply longitudinal modulus	$E_x = 2.13 \times 10^7$ psi
Ply transverse modulus	$E_y = 1.65 \times 10^6$ psi
In-plane shear modulus	$G_{xy} = 8.97 \times 10^5$ psi
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{xy} = 0.3$
Ply longitudinal tensile strength	$X_t = 2.51 \times 10^5$ psi
Ply longitudinal compressive strength	$X_c = 2.00 \times 10^5$ psi
Ply shear strength	$S_c = 1.94 \times 10^4$ psi
Ply transverse tensile strength	$Y_t = 9.65 \times 10^3$ psi
Ply transverse compressive strength	$Y_c = 3.89 \times 10^4$ psi

As shown in Figure 2, an excellent agreement was found between the predicted strengths and the data. The predicted mode of failure for all cases considered coincided with the experimental failure modes, either tension or shear-out. It is worth noting that even for $[(\pm 45)]_s$ and $[(0/90)]_s$ laminates with extreme nonlinear behavior, the calculated strengths agreed with the data within 20 percent.

Damage Assessment

The effect of ply orientation on the damage growth as a result of the load increase in the joint could also be determined by performing the code. For instance, the relationship between the load applied and the area damaged during loading was established for joints with three different ply orientations and are presented in Figures 3-5. From the figures, it is clearly indicated that the load-damage area curves strongly depend on ply orientation and geometry of the joint.

For the joint with $[(0/\pm 45/90)_3]_s$ laminates and in tension failure mode, the predicted damage area was very confined to the area near the stress concentrations even when the applied load was up to 90% of the maximum load. However, damage was initiated at a very early stage of loading. For $[(0/90)_6]_s$ laminates failed by shear-out mode, the predicted damage area was more extensive than quasi-isotropic laminates, and showed a slightly different trend with regard to the rate of damage growth. More interestingly, the load-damage area curve was a straight line for the joint with $[(\pm 45)_6]_s$ laminates, because both the initial and the final failure loads occurred almost simultaneously.

The damage progression at different load levels corresponding to each of the foregoing laminates is plotted in Figures 6-8, respectively. Only the upper half portion of the joints was shown in these figures. In Figure 6, for the joint with $[(0/\pm 45/90)_3]_s$, damage was initiated by matrix cracking on the hole boundary about 90 degrees from the loading direction at the load of 1700 lbf. At the load of 3100 lbf, multiple failure modes occurred near the hole boundary. Finally, the joint with substantial damage across the width failed at a load of 3200 lbf, after which the joint could not sustain any additional load. The predicted failure load was within 5% of the experimental data, and the predicted mode of failure was tensile, the same as the observed mode.

Damage propagation in the joint with $[(0/90)_6]_s$ is demonstrated in Figure 7. At a load of 1900 lbf, damage was initiated at two different areas; one near 110 degrees but another at about 45 degrees, measured from the loading direction. As the load increased, damage in the latter area extended more substantially than did the damage in the former. Fiber breakage and fiber-matrix shearing were the dominant failure mechanisms in that area. At the load of 2700 lbf, damage quickly extended up to the top of the boundary by fiber-matrix shearing and fiber breakage, resulting in shear-out failure mode. The experimental failure load of the joint was 2650 lbf and the mode of failure was also shear-out.

Damage process as a function of the applied load in a $[(\pm 45)_6]_s$ joint is presented in Figure 8. Due to the nonlinear shear stress-shear strain relations in each ply, the load-displacement relation of the joint was extremely nonlinear. Initially, damage was predicted to take place at the stress concentrations by matrix shearing and near the top of the hole boundary by matrix compression. As the load increased very slightly, damage near the stress concentrations extended more rapidly than that in the bearing area and, then, propagated along the fiber direction (45 degree) as shown in the figure. However, damage continued to grow at the same load until it reached the straight-edge boundary. The specimen failed at the load of 1600 lbf.

Residual Strength Prediction

The effect of initial damage in laminates caused by a pre-load on the strength of the joints was also studied. In this study, joints were first loaded beyond the initial failure load and, then, unloaded and reloaded again until the joints totally failed. Joints with three different ply orientations were considered in the calculations. Each joint was pre-loaded up to 80% of its maximum load, resulting in localized damage near stress concentrations. The predicted residual strength of the joints with the initial damage caused by the pre-load is presented in Table 2. Except for $[(0/90)_6]_s$, the initial damage had no effect on the ultimate strength of the others. Ironically, the residual strength of $[(0/90)_6]_s$ joint increased slightly, which was consistent with the experimental finding [14] of increase in the static strength of $[(0/90)_6]_s$ laminates as a result of an initial damage. It is noted that the predicted residual strength has no relationship with the fatigue strength. However, appropriate fatigue analysis could be incorporated into the model to predict the residual strength of joints caused by fatigue.

TABLE 2
Static Strength of Bolted Composites Containing an Initial Damage Due to Pre-load.
T300/1034-C Graphite-Epoxy

ply orientation	D(in)	W/D	E/D	*Max. Load(lbf) w/o damage	**Max. Load(lbf) with damage
$[(0/\pm 45/90)_3]_s$	0.25	3.0	3.0	3200	3200
$[(90_2/\pm 60/\pm 30)_2]_3$	0.25	3.0	3.0	2100	2100
$[(0/90)_6]_s$	0.25	3.0	3.0	2700	2800

* Virgin laminates

** Laminates containing damage caused by a pre-load of 80% the corresponding maximum load.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the results of the computer simulations, we conclude that

1. the knowledge of damage progression could help in selecting ply orientation and sizing bolted joints made of laminated composites.
2. ply orientation and geometry have significant effects on both strength of and damage in bolted composite joints.
3. initial damage confined to a local area has a limited effect on the static strength of bolted joints in laminated composites.

Therefore, the information provided by the code could be very important in designing joints using advanced composite materials. Further development of the model is necessary to include prediction of the bearing failure mode and fatigue analysis for cyclic loading, which were not taken into account by the present model.

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Figure 1. Description of the problem.

Figure 2. Bearing strengths of T300/1034-C laminates containing a pin-loaded hole. Comparisons between the data and the results of the calculations.

Figure 3. The relationship between the applied load and the damaged area in bolted composite joints made of $[(0/\pm 45/90)_3]_s$ laminates.

Figure 4. The relationship between the applied load and the damaged area in bolted composite joints made of $[(0/90)_6]_s$ laminates.

Figure 5. The relationship between the applied load and the damaged area in bolted composite joints made of [(±45)₆]₃ laminates.

Figure 6. Illustration of damage growth predicted by the code at different load levels. [(0/±45/90)₃]₃ laminate containing a pin-loaded hole. D=0.25 in, W/D=3.0, E/D=3.0.

Figure 7. Illustration of damage growth predicted by the code at different load levels. $[(0/90)_6]_s$ laminate containing a pin-loaded hole. $D=0.25$ in, $W/D=3.0$, $E/D=3.0$.

Figure 8. Illustration of damage growth predicted by the code at different load levels. $[(\pm 45)_6]_s$ laminate containing a pin-loaded hole. $D=0.25$ in, $W/D=3.0$, $E/D=3.0$.